

MS2 Data Management Plan updated

31/12/2025

Abstract

This second Data Management Plan (DMP) introduces a report that outlines the approach adopted for the collection, processing, monitoring, and cataloguing of research data, in accordance with the FAIR principles. Building upon the initial version of the DPM (**D1.2 Data management plan**), this milestone reflects the evolution of data practices throughout the project lifecycle.

Funded by
the European Union

EOOSC Beyond receives funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101131875

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Document Description

MS2 Data Management Plan updated			
Work Package Number 1			
Due date	31/12/2025	Actual delivery date:	19/12/2025
Nature of document	Report	Dissemination level	Public
Document Status	Under EC review	Version	1.0
Lead Partner	EGI Foundation		
Authors	Elena Motovska (EGI)		
Document link	https://documents.egi.eu/secure/ShowDocument?docid=4224		
DOI	https://zenodo.org/records/17984710		
Keyword	Data Management Plan, FAIR, GDPR, metadata, reusable data		

Revision History

Issue	Date	Description	Author/Reviewer
V 0.1	05/12/2025	Initial first input	Elena Motovska (EGI)
V 0.2	12/12/2025	Finalised and ready for review	Elena Motovska (EGI)
V 0.3	15/12/2025	Internal review	Hien Bui (EGI)
V 0.4	17/12/2025	Approval from the Board	WPLG
V 1.0	19/12/2025	Final	Elena Motovska (EGI)

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Executive Summary

This is an updated version of the original EOSC Beyond Data Management Plan (DMP) (D1.2) submitted at M06. It includes an additional chapter specifying the dataset produced by each use case (pilot nodes)/WPs over the course of the project, which were not fully clarified at the time of the first version.

Key Points of the DMP include:

- **Data Types and Formats:** The DMP identifies various types of data—textual, numerical, software code, multimedia, and presentations—produced within the project. Each data type is managed according to its specific requirements to ensure it remains accessible and reusable long after the project's conclusion.
- **FAIR Data Management:** The DMP provides a detailed plan for making data FAIR, including the use of standardised metadata, open repositories like Zenodo and GitHub, and interoperability standards such as Darwin Core and JSON. The plan also outlines the use of tools such as the F-UJI API to assess and improve data findability.
- **Data Security and Ethical Considerations:** The document addresses the security of both personal and open data, ensuring compliance with GDPR and other relevant regulations. It outlines procedures for anonymising personal data and safeguarding sensitive information, with clear protocols for data breaches and ethical management.
- **Resource Allocation and Responsibilities:** The DMP details the allocation of resources for data management activities and defines the roles and responsibilities of project participants. This includes the task leaders, WP leaders, and data managers, who are responsible for ensuring data quality and compliance with the DMP.
- **Change management for the DMP:** The DMP is maintained and updated during the project to reflect the most recent developments and conclusions.

The EOSC Beyond project adheres to Horizon Europe Open Science FAIR principles and strives to make data as open as possible and as closed as necessary. The beneficiaries share the project's data in a manner that makes it valuable to partners and their users outside the project, while ensuring that the privacy of third parties who participated in the data collection/generation is not compromised.

Under these conditions, the data will be managed and released in compliance with the certifications and safeguards of the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). Every dataset is examined (in terms of sensitivity, privacy, and security) before an official decision is made on whether or not to make that specific information public.

1. Introduction

1.1. Purpose and Scope of the document

Milestone 2 (MS2) represents an updated version of **D1.2 Data Management Plan**. The updated plan provides a comprehensive overview of the standards effectively used, the storage and publication mechanisms implemented, and the measures taken to ensure data verification and reuse. MS2 consolidates the data management frameworks, building upon the initial structure and preliminary guidelines. The Data Management Plan has been progressively updated to reflect the evolution of data handling within the EOSC Beyond project.

In principle, the DMP describes the standards that are being used, and how the project's research data are stored and published for verification and reuse. EOSC Beyond aims for full open access to data, following the FAIR principles. The updated DMP covers all aspects of data management, from the types of data collected and the methodologies for their storage and dissemination to the ethical considerations and intellectual property rights associated with the data.

1.2. Structure of the Document

This document is comprised of the following chapters:

Section 1: presents an introduction to the project and the document.

Section 2: presents the purpose of data collection, type and format, and origin of the data.

Section 3: outlines EOSC Beyond FAIR data strategies.

Section 4: briefly describes the allocation of resources.

Sections 5 and **6**: outline data security, ethical issues.

Section 7: section concludes this milestone.

Section 8: shows the datasets of Work Packages (WPs).

Section 9: shows the datasets Use Cases.

2. Overview of the Data

In this chapter, we describe how are the various types of data the EOSC Beyond consortium being handled during the project's lifetime. Some assets were managed directly by the WPs, while others were managed by scientific communities independently.

2.1. Data Assets Generated by the Project

The EOSC Beyond project generates and manages various types of data, including software, workflows, publications, and documentation. Data will be stored in a way that adheres to the FAIR principles, ensuring findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability.

2.2. Types of Data Generated and Collected

The project manages various types of data, including but not limited to, in addition to publications and documentation:

- **Textual data:** This includes documents, reports, publications, project deliverables, and meeting minutes. These are typically stored in formats such as .doc/.docx, .txt, and .pdf.
- **Numerical Data:** This comprises datasets that involve numerical information, including but not limited to, statistics, measurements, and quantitative research results. These are commonly stored in formats like .csv, .xls/.xlsx, and .json.
- **Geospatial Data:** This category includes data with geographic components, such as coordinates, maps, or location-based information. Geospatial data can be stored in formats like **.shp**, **.geojson**, **.gml**, **.kml**, and **.tiff** for raster data. These datasets are typically used for mapping, spatial analysis, and geographic visualisation.
- **Semantic Data:** This includes structured data enriched with meaning, often represented through ontologies, taxonomies, and controlled vocabularies. It supports interoperability and advanced data querying. Semantic data can be stored in formats like **.rdf**, **.owl**, and **.ttl**, which are commonly used for knowledge graphs, linked data, and semantic web technologies.
- **Code and Software:** The project produces source code and software tools that support data analysis, processing, and visualisation. These are stored in formats such as .py, .R, .m, and other relevant programming languages. Software repositories like GitHub are used for storage and version control.
- **Multimedia Records:** This category includes images, videos, and audio files that capture visual or auditory data relevant to the project. The formats include .jpg/.jpeg, .png, .gif for images; .mp4 for videos; and .wav for audio files.
- **Presentations:** Visual aids and slide decks used for project meetings, dissemination events, and educational purposes. These will be saved in formats like .ppt/.pptx for editable presentations and .pdf for final versions.
- **Metadata** This category includes descriptive, structural, and administrative information about the above resource within the project. Metadata helps in

organising, searching, and understanding the context of the data. Common formats for metadata include .xml, .json, .yaml, and .rdf, and metadata standards such as Dublin Core, ISO 19115 for geospatial data, or DCAT for datasets.

These formats ensure that the project outputs are accessible, interoperable, and reusable, adhering to the FAIR principles. The selection of specific formats is guided by community standards and the nature of the data or document.

2.3. Existing data/software and newly generated project outputs

The EOSC Beyond project builds on both existing datasets and software as well as newly generated outputs, which are crucial to achieving the project's objectives. EOSC Beyond leverages existing data and software components that are foundational to the project's work. These include:

Existing Data:

- **Climate Data:** Gridded climate datasets from previous projects, particularly those conforming to CMIP standards, which provide a basis for further research and analysis.
- **Biodiversity Data:** Information about species distribution, population, taxonomy, and ecosystems. Examples include species occurrence data, ecological community data, and biodiversity assessments.
- **Geospatial Data:** spatial data that links for example ecological and biodiversity information to geographical locations, or data that enable spatial analysis of social phenomena.
- **Genomic and Metagenomic Data:** Data related to species' genetic sequences and metagenomic analysis for understanding biodiversity at the molecular level.
- **Proteomic data:** Data related to protein expression, structures, and functions, including mass spectrometry results and protein-protein interaction studies.
- **Molecular Biology Data:** Datasets from molecular and cellular biology experiments, including gene expression profiles, molecular signaling pathways, and regulatory networks
- **Biotechnological and life sciences data:** Data from computational models and simulations of biological systems, including systems biology models, metabolic pathways, and protein folding simulations
- **Remote Sensing Data:** Satellite and aerial imagery are collected to monitor land use, habitat changes, and environmental phenomena.
- **Survey Data:** Large-scale datasets from national or international social surveys. These datasets typically include responses to structured questionnaires covering areas such as demographics, social behavior, attitudes, and opinions.
- **Historical Data:** Data sets covering past social, economic, or demographic trends. This can include archived survey data or reconstructed datasets from older censuses or historical research projects.

- **Microdata:** Anonymized datasets that provide individual-level data, often derived from surveys, censuses, or administrative records. These datasets are used for in-depth analysis of individual or household characteristics.
- **Cross-National Comparative Data:** Harmonised datasets from multiple countries, allowing for cross-national comparisons of social phenomena like employment, income distribution, public opinion, or health outcomes. Examples include data from international surveys like the European Social Survey (ESS) and Eurobarometer.
- **Food Composition Data:** like nutrient profiles and bioactive compounds.
- **Food Safety Data:** Contaminants Data, Data on the presence of chemical contaminants (e.g., pesticides, heavy metals, mycotoxins), microbial contaminants (e.g., pathogens), and allergens in food products; Residue Analysis: Data on residues from veterinary drugs, food contact materials, and other chemicals that may be found in food.
- **Traceability and Provenance Data and other kinds of data coming from the METROFOOD-RI:** Data tracking the origin and movement of food products across the supply chain, ensuring authenticity and compliance with safety regulations.
- **Metadata Repositories:** Established metadata repositories such as CESSDA Data Catalogue or LifeWatch ERIC Metadata Catalogue, which will serve as a reference for ensuring that new data generated by EOSC Beyond is discoverable and interoperable.

Existing Software

- **Analysis Tools:** Established software tools: Jupyter Notebooks and Python scripts used for climate data analysis and visualisation, web services, F-UJI API for findability assessment of the content.
- **Data Management Platforms:** Platforms like the ESGF (Earth System Grid Federation) and existing open-source repositories (e.g., GitHub) where pre-existing code and workflows are maintained and continuously improved.
- **Catalogues and marketplaces:** Platform offering access to a wide range of research data, services, and tools. Researchers can discover, access, and share data, and also contribute their own resources.
- **Core Services:** a set of foundational services enabling the integration and interoperability of diverse research resources in the EOSC ecosystem. It includes authentication, authorisation, persistent identifiers, and monitoring tools.
- **HelpDesk:** a centralised support service offering help to users navigating EOSC resources. It provides technical assistance, guidance on using services, and support for onboarding new resources.
- **Other services (software)** like platforms offering training modules and resources aimed at improving researchers' skills in open science practices and data management. EOSC Beyond is not responsible for external data/software but will rely on them as a foundation.

Individual DMPs are maintained by service owners for these existing datasets and software, ensuring they are used appropriately within the project's scope.

Newly Generated Project Outputs

The project generates a wide range of new data and software outputs, which are carefully managed and documented to ensure they adhere to FAIR principles. These outputs include:

Newly Generated Data:

- **Research Data:** This includes newly collected experimental data, survey results, and other forms of primary data specific to the research objectives of EOSC Beyond.
- **Knowledge Graph Data:** Generated as part of the project's effort to interlink datasets and metadata, facilitating enhanced search and discovery functionalities within the EOSC ecosystem.
- **Service-Specific Datasets:** Data produced by specific services within the EOSC Beyond project, which will be catalogued and stored following best practices in data management.

Newly Developed Software:

- **Custom Tools:** Software specifically developed during the project to address unique research needs, including enhanced versions of existing tools or entirely new applications.
- **Workflows and Scripts:** New workflows, including those for data processing, analysis, and visualization, particularly in Python and other relevant programming languages. These are documented and shared through platforms like GitHub to ensure reusability.
- **API Integrations, Connectors:** APIs developed to enhance interoperability between datasets and services, conforming to international standards to facilitate integration within the broader EOSC infrastructure.

New Metadata, EOSC Beyond can produce enhanced metadata that ensures data and services compliance with the **FAIR** principles, which are essential for making data & services easy to find, access, and reuse across different research domains. All newly generated project outputs are stored in open repositories, such as Zenodo and GitHub, under appropriate open licences (e.g., CC BY for data and permissive open-source licences for software). This ensures that the outputs are accessible, interoperable, and reusable by the broader research community.

3. FAIR Data

In this section, we outline the EOSC Beyond policies and best practices concerning FAIR publication of research data assets. interTwin is committed to the publication of research data according to the FAIR principles. The EOSC Beyond consortium is dedicated to guaranteeing that every dataset created, handled, and shared throughout the project adheres to the FAIR principles. This commitment extends to every phase of the data lifecycle, including collection, storage, curation, publication, and long-term preservation.

To ensure that data is FAIR, EOSC Beyond implements recognised standards such as the Darwin Core and JSON for data interoperability, and utilise tools like the F-UJI API to assess and enhance findability scores, particularly for datasets in repositories like CESSDA Data Catalogue. Additionally, OAI-PMH (Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting) employs to facilitate metadata sharing across repositories.

3.1. Making data findable, including provisions of metadata

Data is designed to be FAIR and is made available as openly and as early as possible. Data is only restricted when required by regulatory or legal constraints or due to the owner's legitimate interests. Raw data from consultations (like user surveys and questionnaires) are aggregated and anonymised to ensure it can be reused for future purposes.

3.1.1. Metadata

Metadata adheres to a standardised schema based on community standards, ensuring consistency across all data types. The metadata required by data repositories is used as outlined in **Table 1**. For documents, EOSC Beyond has defined a standard set of metadata to ensure consistent and comprehensive documentation of data assets as shown in **Table 2**. Metadata is created and managed using tools like OpenAIRE Argos to ensure compatibility with FAIR principles and interoperability across repositories

Element	Definition
Title	A name given to the source.
Upload type	e.g., dataset, workflow, project deliverables
Abstract	Describing the document contents and main conclusions
Submitter	The person submitting the document to the repository
Authors	The people involved in contributing to a significant portion of the data
DOI	Provided by the resource
Publication date	The date of first publication
Version	The version number generated by the document repository for the repository identifier. Versioning rule: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • +0.1 – a new version of the draft • +1.0 – a new version of the approved document
Language	A language of the intellectual content of the resource.
Keywords	A list of words that will support the search within the repository service.

Communities	A specific community in which the upload will appear.
License	Specifies the copyright status under which the upload will be licensed.
Modify	The groups can modify the document. The 'EGI office' SSO group must be always marked.

Table 1: Repository metadata

Element	Definition
Title	A name given to the source. For milestones and deliverables as described in the Description of Work.
Lead Partner	The recognised short name of the lead partner within the EOSC Beyond project
Authors	The people involved in writing significant portions of the document.
Reviewers	The people involved in reviewing the document.
Approved by	The board involved in approving the document
Copyright status	Public material is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License . Confidential material may not be reproduced, distributed, or disclosed in whole or in part without the prior written consent of the EOSC Beyond consortium
Document Type	e.g., deliverable, report, white paper
Status	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Draft - the document is being prepared ● Under EC review - the document is submitted to the EC portal and has not yet been approved by the European Commission ● Approved by EC - the document is approved by the EC ● Final - status of the document
Dissemination Level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Public - can be shared without restrictions ● Confidential - can be shared only with European Commission and project partners
Document link	The URL in the document repository that provides access to the document on the EGI Document Repository (DocDB).
DOI	An identification number is assigned through a repository service.
Keywords	A list of words that will support the search within the document repositories.
Abstract	Describing the document contents and main conclusions.

Table 2: Document metadata

3.1.2. Metadata Standards and Implementation

Metadata are generated in accordance with widely accepted community standards to ensure consistency, interoperability, and ease of discovery across different data types. Specifically:

- **Darwin Core:** This standard is used for biodiversity data, ensuring that datasets are interoperable with other international biodiversity databases. For instance, species occurrence data collected during the project will include metadata fields such as scientific name, location, and date of observation, following the Darwin Core schema. This enables seamless integration with global biodiversity platforms like GBIF (Global Biodiversity Information Facility).
- **JSON-LD:** For linked data and semantic web applications, we utilise JSON-LD (JavaScript Object Notation for Linked Data) to structure metadata in a machine-readable format. This facilitates the integration of EOSC Beyond datasets

with other datasets on the web, enabling advanced data analytics and discovery. For example, metadata describing climate model outputs are structured in JSON-LD to allow easy linking with external climate data repositories.

3.1.3. Justification for Metadata Choices

The selection of Darwin Core and JSON-LD as metadata standards is based on their wide acceptance and ability to support the specific data types generated by EOSC Beyond and their advantages with interoperability. Darwin Core is a globally recognized standard for biodiversity data, ensuring that our datasets are compatible with international repositories. JSON-LD is chosen for its flexibility in representing structured data and its compatibility with modern web technologies, making it ideal for datasets that require high levels of interoperability and machine-readability.

3.2. Making data openly accessible

Textual outputs such as reports and presentations are available to the EOSC Beyond Community on Zenodo upon release, under a permissive licence like CC BY. Sensitive legal, personal, or financial information are restricted to authorised project partners, with access controls managed through secure platforms like the EGI Document Repository. All data are accessible via a standard URL or DOI, with metadata openly available to ensure comprehensive documentation and discoverability. Special consideration is given to personal data, which is anonymised before sharing, and proprietary data, which is subject to access restrictions as per legal agreements.

3.2.1. Repositories

All documents, presentations and other materials that form an official output of the project (not just milestones and deliverables) are placed in the EGI's trusted **document repository** to provide a managed central location for all materials.

In addition, public deliverables and publications are shared publicly via the **Zenodo platform** to increase the discoverability of the project outputs. Zenodo assigns a resolvable DOI to all submissions and exports metadata in standards such as Dublin Core and DataCite Metadata Schema. All profiles, specifications, configuration files, software, workflows, and code are deposited in Zenodo. Therefore, EOSC Beyond will use DocDB, Zenodo, and GitHub as their standard and main repositories.

3.2.2. Standardised access protocol

All data are accessible via a uniform resource locator (URL) or Document Object Identifier (DOI). There are no restrictions on the use of the research outputs, both during and after the end of this project.

3.2.3. Metadata availability

Metadata containing information to enable users to access the data are openly available and published together with the data, in the same repositories as listed under **Repositories**. There is no time limit on metadata and data availability.

The EOSC Beyond project acknowledges the value of documentation for interoperability purposes, increases uptake by different communities, and encourages data owners to document their research data assets. EOSC Beyond does not enforce specific provisions on documentation as long as the data asset is hosted on one of the mentioned repositories and properly curated according to the repository's best practices.

Research data itself should not be considered self-documenting and each published asset must be associated with sufficient documentation resources accessible through a public URL. Documentation must be browsable and include hypertext references to facilitate its fruition. Recommended documentation formats include markdown, HTML, and other markup languages. The inclusion of machine-readable documentation such as OpenAPI where applicable is thoroughly encouraged. If a scientific publication is tied to the research data asset, the publication itself should be referenced and/or made available as part of the documentation.

3.2.4. Making data interoperable

The EOSC Beyond consortium acknowledges the importance of data interoperability: if a data asset cannot be compared, merged, or otherwise integrated with other assets, then its publication would bring little or no value to the community. The consortium is therefore committed to supporting and enforcing data interoperability.

3.2.5. Increasing data re-use

Data and outputs are licensed under open, permissive licences to maximise reusability. For example, CMIP6 outputs are publicly accessible, and tools will be available through GitHub for further development and reuse.

4. Allocation of Resources

Any expenses associated with the collection/production of FAIR data during the EOSC Beyond activities are included in the project budget. These expenditures are required to cover a variety of particular data processing and data management operations, ranging from data collection and documentation to storage and preservation to distribution and re-utilization. These operations are a component of the Work Packages (WPs) that process the relevant data, hence the needed effort is part of the relevant WP.

The expenses of long-term data preservation are minimal, by using the EGI Online Storage and Google Drive platforms. Using Zenodo and GitHub (both free of charge) ensures that costs for long-term preservation of the data are manageable. Zenodo supports the long-term preservation of data deposits, with the repository projected to be maintained for at least the next twenty years by the host laboratory CERN (see Retention period in Zenodo policies: <https://about.zenodo.org/policies/>). When applicable, a more accurate cost estimate will be provided at a later stage of the project.

4.1. Data Management responsibilities

Within the EOSC Beyond project, the following roles and responsibilities are associated with Data Management, which are defined as follow:

- **WP leaders** are in charge of organising the data processing and quality assurance that take place inside the Work Package they are leading.
- **Task Leaders** are responsible for compiling and producing data within their assigned tasks. In addition to that, they also make sure that the data are properly prepared to be shared among the partners, and made publicly available, when applicable.
- **Data users** are consortium partners who use, e.g., processing operations on the compiled/produced data.
- **Quality and Risk Manager** monitors and supports the WP leaders, and Task Leaders/Use Case leaders in keeping the DMP confluence pages up to date. In addition, reports the changes and processes via milestones and deliverables as specified in the Grand Agreement.

5. Data Security

All gathered data is securely handled throughout the entire duration of the EOSC Beyond project, to protect it from loss and unauthorised access. Personal data is only accessible to those who are authorised¹ to access it.

All partners/beneficiaries responsible for processing personal data² have the responsibility to ensure that the data remains protected under all necessary security controls (including backup policies and integrity checks³) and access controls (identification, authentication, authorisation) within their infrastructure. In the unfortunate event of a personal data breach, the project partners will notify without delay their competent national supervisory authorities as well as the data subject(s) that may be affected by the breach. At the same time, they will document any personal data breaches and all related information.

Regarding open data, for security and long-term preservation, EOSC Beyond relies on the EGI Document Repository, Zenodo, Google Drive and GitHub platforms.

¹ Personal contact data are collected during the EGI SSO (Single Sign On) account creation by the users. After the access is granted, the users can manage their data in autonomy.

² Processing, according to Regulation (EU) 2017/679 of the European Parliament (GDPR), means any operation or set of operations which is performed on personal data or on sets of personal data, whether by automated means, such as collection, recording, organisation, structuring, storage, adaptation or alteration, retrieval, consultation, use, disclosure by transmission, dissemination or otherwise making available, alignment or combination, restriction, erasure, or destruction.

³ The integrity check is the process of comparing the current state of stored data and/or programs to a previously recorded state to determine any alteration or change.

6. Ethical Aspect

Ethical and legal issues within the EOSC Beyond project are handled meticulously to ensure full compliance with relevant regulations, including GDPR, and to protect the rights and privacy of all individuals involved in or affected by the research. The following strategies will be employed, with specific examples and procedures to illustrate their application:

- **Anonymisation of Personal Data:** For datasets that include personal data, such as survey responses or interview transcripts, we implement a two-step anonymisation process. First, direct identifiers (e.g., names, addresses) are removed. Second, indirect identifiers (e.g., job titles, locations) are generalised or removed. For example, instead of recording “CEO of a specific company,” we use “senior management position in the technology sector.” This approach ensures that no identification of natural persons is possible, thus protecting individual privacy and complying with GDPR requirements.
- **Restricted Data Dissemination:** In cases where legal agreements limit the dissemination of certain datasets (e.g., proprietary research data or third-party owned datasets), the data itself is not made available. However, descriptive metadata, including the type of data, its purpose, and conditions for access, is published to maintain transparency. For instance, if a dataset is restricted due to intellectual property agreements, we include metadata that specifies how interested parties can request access under specific conditions.
- **Handling of Personal Data:** Personal data related to EOSC Core Innovation Sandbox users or Providers are securely stored and are not shared outside the consortium. For example, user registration data (such as email addresses) are protected through appropriate technical and organisational measures to ensure data security. These measures include access restricted for authorised personnel only and regular audits to ensure that data handling practices comply with GDPR and other relevant regulations.

7. Conclusion and Next Steps

EOSC Beyond DMP is a complete data management approach that complies with Horizon Europe recommendations and that aims to make data as findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable (FAIR) as feasible.

Relying on robust technological solutions and standards, such as the EGI Document Repository, Zenodo, GitHub and Google Drive⁴ for the execution of these processes. Additionally, this ensures that the data created or compiled throughout the EOSC Beyond project, including open data and public publications, is kept and continues to be usable once the project is completed.

The plan is intended to safeguard the analysis of compiled/created data based on the privacy level and to use an alternate sharing methodology relying upon this level. Confidential information or information that raises ethical problems are not released. Finally, the DMP is built on guaranteeing appropriately informed consent and protecting each participant's zone of privacy, while adhering to GDPR guidelines.

8.1. DMP Change Management

This DMP is considered a living document and will be updated during the project to reflect the most recent developments and conclusions. In actuality, this updated version of the DMP will be refined and finalised at M36 of the project. Ad hoc improvements may also be deployed if deemed necessary. In general, changes need to be fully compliant with EU laws and best practices in research data management.

This updated version also includes a Chapter specifying the dataset produced by each use case (pilot nodes)/WPs over the course of the project. Updates will be entered in the changelog table that is shown on the confluence page of the concerned DMP. Analogously, the distribution of notifications on updates will be realised via regular meetings (WPs, PMO, TCB).

⁴ Google is listed in the DPF and thus, covered by EU-U.S. Data Privacy Framework <https://www.dataprivacyframework.gov/list>. All instances of Jira, GitHub, Confluence are operated on European Servers and compliant with GDPR.

8. Data sets for WPs

Work Package	WP1 - WP16
Contact	Work Package Leaders
Data Summary	
Data description: Types of data	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Project Documentation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Metrics ● Risks, Procedures, Plans ● Meetings agenda, participation list and minutes ● Presentations ● Deliverables ● Mailing list archive ● External Feedback (surveys, events, etc) ● Promotional material (flyers, posters, branding materials, support materials such as factsheets, eBooks, slide decks, etc.) ● Other communication & dissemination material (multimedia, video, etc) 2. Project Datasets <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EOSC Metadata Knowledge Graph ● EOSC Beyond Ontology and Resource Profiles
Data description: Origin of data	All the data will be produced and provided by project members.
Data description: Scale of data	<1GB
Standards and metadata	<p>Plain text such as .docx, .txt, .rtf, .pdf, .pptx, xml, .xls, .html. Multimedia such as jpg/jpeg, gif, tiff, png or video formats</p> <p>Metadata Knowledge Graph: tar archive of json files</p> <p>EOSC Beyond Ontology and Resource Profiles: xls file and documentation</p>
Data sharing: Target groups	<p>All project members and the EC Project office.</p> <p>Communication activities; is publicly available focusing on the target audiences of the project: including users, technology providers and infrastructure providers</p>
Data sharing: Scientific Impact	Scientific Publications in peer-reviewed journals, conferences & events aiming to engage stakeholders

Data sharing: Approach to sharing	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Shared within the consortium and European Commission <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presentations: Public presentations are made public via indico portal or external conference pages • Deliverables: All deliverables are shared within the consortium and also with the European Commission. Public deliverables are accessible to everyone via the project website and Zenodo portal. • Mailing list archive: only accessible by the mailing list members. • Publications will be available via the project website and EOSC Data Commons community on Zenodo Repository. • Promotional and other audio-visual material will be available via the project website and EOSC Beyond YouTube channel. • Datasets published on the Zenodo community of the EOSC Beyond project 2. Shared with the Project office and management boards to support work, as well as with the European Commission. <p>Unless otherwise stated all content will be available under the CC BY 4.0 license and metadata under the CC0 license. Any consortium-restricted content is shared via access-protected confluence space.</p>
Archiving and preservation	<p>Once the project is finished, all the information will be preserved by the EGI Foundation for at least 5 years as well on the EC funding portal.</p> <p>Publications and datasets will also be kept in the Zenodo Community.</p>
Allocation of resources	
Who will be responsible for data management in your WP/Task?	Work Package Leaders
How will long-term preservation be ensured?	<p>Long-term preservation is not needed, except from the contractual 5 years after the project. A copy of all the documentation of the project is kept by the European Commission in the funding portal. Deliverables, publications and other dissemination material are shared via the Zenodo portal, which grants long-term preservation</p>
Data Security	
What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?	<p>To access the data shared only within the consortium, an EGI SSO account is required. Accounts and access management is the responsibility of the coordinator.</p>
Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long-term preservation and curation?	<p>For security and long-term preservation, EOSC Data Commons relies on EGI Document Repository, Zenodo and Google Drive platforms.</p>
Other issues	

<i>Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones?</i>	EGI Foundation will take care of the data according to the ISO 27000 standard for Information security management and GDPR.
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9. Datasets per Use case

9.1. Instruct-ERIC

Work Package/Task	WP15/T15.2, WP16/T16.2
Contact	Marcus Povey, Yvonne de Jong-Leung, Marcus Lowndes
Established a DMP, addressing important aspects of RDM.	In progress
Data Summary	
Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for?	<p>Instruct-ERIC will be processing and handling research data as part of its data storage user story, and then publish metadata about the stored data (after embargo) to public repositories, including a link to access. The data itself will not be reused for Instruct-ERIC purposes, but may be reused by the broader research community according to FAIR principles.</p> <p>The metadata may be reused by Instruct-ERIC to produce metrics or knowledge graphs to produce insights about what kind of technologies are being used, and how.</p>
Will you re-use any existing data and will this generate new data?	<p>Actual stored data will not be reused within the project or by Instruct-ERIC. Researchers in the community may access and reuse the published data and may produce new statistical analyses, reinterpretations, or review articles using the data.</p> <p>Instruct-ERIC will use the metadata to produce new statistical analyses, metrics, knowledge graphs, etc</p>
What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?	<p>Metadata will be produced in common machine-readable formats such as JSON and XML following standards, including ISO19139 and EML 2.2.0.</p> <p>Statistical analyses may also use other file formats such as CSV, or .xlsx</p>
What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?	Providing open and FAIR access to research data produced in EU and RI funded research access visits
What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?	Metadata records: < 500MB
What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?	The metadata will originate from the facility that produced it, and funding body that provided access
To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?	Wider research community. In the initial stages, these will be structural biologists with specialisations in the technologies of the research visits that metadata will be produced from, e.g., Cryo-EM, NMR, etc
FAIR Data	

1.) Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	<p><i>Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?</i></p> <p>Yes</p> <p><i>Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.</i></p> <p>Metadata will follow data cite guidelines</p> <p><i>Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?</i></p> <p>Yes</p>
2.) Making data openly accessible	
a) Repository:	<p><i>Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?</i></p> <p>Yes, metadata will be stored in Instruct ARIA and published to OpenAIRE</p> <p><i>Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?</i></p> <p>Yes, talks are ongoing</p> <p><i>Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?</i></p> <p>Yes</p>
b) Data:	<p><i>Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.</i></p> <p>Metadata: Yes</p> <p>Stored data: Yes, after embargo</p> <p><i>If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek the protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.</i></p> <p>Currently undecided</p> <p><i>Will the data be accessible through a free and standardised access protocol?</i></p> <p>Yes?</p> <p><i>If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?</i></p> <p>Embargo period for access to metadata</p>

	<p><i>How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?</i></p> <p>The metadata will be publically available</p>
	<p><i>Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?</i></p> <p>No</p>
c) Metadata:	<p><i>Will metadata be made openly available and licensed under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?</i></p> <p>Yes</p>
	<p><i>How long will the data remain available and findable?</i></p> <p>Permanent</p>
	<p><i>Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?</i></p> <p>Yes</p>
	<p><i>Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read or process the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open-source code)?</i></p> <p>Yes, fandanGO is open source</p>
3.) Making data interoperable	<p><i>What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?</i></p> <p>No</p>
	<p><i>In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project-specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining, or extending them?</i></p> <p>N/A</p>
	<p><i>Will your data include qualified references to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?</i></p> <p>No</p>
4.) Increase data re-use	<p><i>How will you provide the documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?</i></p> <p>N/A</p>

	<p><i>Will your data be made openly available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard re-use licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement? Under which license?</i></p> <p>Yes, although pilot only has dummy data</p> <p><i>Will the data produced in the project be usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?</i></p> <p>N/A</p> <p><i>Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?</i></p> <p>N/A</p> <p><i>Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.</i></p> <p>N/A</p> <p><i>Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security, and ethical aspects.</i></p>
What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?	To access the data shared only within the consortium, an EGI SSO account is required. Accounts and access management is the responsibility of the coordinator.
Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long-term preservation and curation?	For security and long-term preservation, EOSC Data Commons relies on EGI Document Repository, Zenodo and Google Drive platforms.
Other research outputs	
In addition to the management of data, are you also considering and planning for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout the projects?	<p><i>Such outputs can be either digital (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g. new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.) Are those also following FAIR principles?</i></p> <p>New software developments are open source and published to a public GitHub</p>
Allocation of resources	
Who will be responsible for data management in your WP/Task?	Instruct-ERIC, OneData (for storage)
How will long-term preservation be ensured?	<p><i>(costs and potential value, who decides and how what data will be kept and for how long)</i></p> <p>Pilot data preserved in OneData for lifetime of project, Metadata deposited in OpenAIRE</p>

Data Security	
What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?	Data protection agreement Service level agreement
Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long-term preservation and curation?	Yes, metadata will be stored long-term in Instruct ARIA and permanently published to OpenAIRE
Ethical Aspects	
Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?	<i>Yes or No. (If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action DoA).</i> No
Will informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?	N/A
Other issues	
Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departamental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones?	<i>Please list and briefly describe them.</i>

9.2. ENES

Work Package	WP16/T16.3
Contact	Fabrizio Antonio, Sandro Fiore
Established a DMP, addressing important aspects of RDM.	In progress
Data Summary	
Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for?	Data from public repositories will be used for enabling scientific use cases related to data analysis and visualization: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CMIP6 climate projection data • ERA5 reanalysis data
Will you re-use any existing data and will this generate new data?	No new data is generated from existing data.
What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NetCDF and Zarr formats for scientific data • TOSCA templates (e.g., yaml format) for service deployment. • PROV-JSON Provenance documents • Provenance associated artifacts
What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?	Enable the scientific use case stories defined for the ENES pilot node, thus showcasing a smooth integration of the EOSC Core services within the pilot infrastructure.
What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?	The expected overall size is of TB order.
What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CMIP6 data from the ESGF (Earth System Grid Federation) infrastructure • ERA5 reanalysis from Copernicus Climate Data Store
To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scientists • Research groups • Communities and Organisations • Research Infrastructures • Education and Training Institutions • Learners
FAIR Data	
1.) Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	<p><i>Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?</i></p> <p>PID identifies scientific data in the related repositories. Output products (including provenance documents) do not have a PID because these are generated on demand by the pilot node users.</p> <p><i>Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your</i></p>

	<p><i>discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.</i></p> <p>Scientific data is in NetCDF format, with related metadata defined according to the CF conventions and CMIP Specifications, stored in the file header.</p> <p><i>Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?</i></p> <p>Metadata includes search keywords defined by the CF-Conventions and CMIP Specifications.</p>
2.) Making data openly accessible	
<p>a) Repository:</p>	<p><i>Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?</i></p> <p>Scientific data is stored in trusted repositories. Data resulting from the applications is not deposited.</p> <p>Provenance documents are stored in provenance store services.</p> <p><i>Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?</i></p> <p>Not needed.</p> <p><i>Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?</i></p> <p>Yes.</p>
<p>b) Data:</p>	<p><i>Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.</i></p> <p>All data is openly available to the users.</p> <p><i>If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek the protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.</i></p> <p>Not Applicable.</p> <p><i>Will the data be accessible through a free and standardised access protocol?</i></p> <p>Yes.</p> <p><i>If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?</i></p> <p>Input data is openly available from the related repositories.</p> <p><i>How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?</i></p> <p>For data from Copernicus, such as ERA5, an account on C3S is required. Other data is openly accessible (including provenance documents).</p>

	<p><i>Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?</i></p> <p>No</p>
<p>c) Metadata:</p>	<p><i>Will metadata be made openly available and licensed under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?</i></p> <p>All metadata for the scientific dataset is openly available and described in related documentation (e.g., CF conventions and CMIP specifications for CMIP6).</p> <p><i>How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data is expected to be available on the respective repositories in the long term. • Metadata is expected to be available on the respective indexes in the long term. <p><i>Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read or process the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open-source code)?</i></p> <p>The software packages and libraries are made publicly available on GitHub and are detailed in deliverables. Additionally, all the dependencies needed to handle the data are open source.</p>
<p>3.) Making data interoperable</p>	<p><i>What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?</i></p> <p>Data follows the CF-conventions and CMIP specifications (to the maximum extent possible) for the metadata and is stored as NetCDF and Zarr formats (both standard and de facto in the community).</p> <p>Provenance documents are stored in PROV-JSON formats and follow W3C PROV family of standards and are available through RESTful interface.</p> <p><i>In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project-specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining, or extending them?</i></p> <p>Not applicable.</p> <p><i>Will your data include qualified references to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?</i></p> <p>Not applicable.</p>

<p>4.) Increase data re-use</p>	<p><i>How will you provide the documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?</i></p> <p>Via Jupyter Notebook and readme files openly available on GitHub.</p> <p><i>Will your data be made openly available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard re-use licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement? Under which license?</i></p> <p>The main project outputs consist of template files (e.g., TOSCA templates) that describe how to model, deploy, and manage the ENES pilot node applications and services in a standardized, portable, and interoperable way. These are available on GitHub under the Apache-2.0 license.</p> <p><i>Will the data produced in the project be usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?</i></p> <p>Any material will remain openly available on GitHub after the project ends.</p> <p><i>Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?</i></p> <p>Provenance information is provided according to W3C PROV standards.</p> <p><i>Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.</i></p> <p>Not applicable.</p> <p><i>Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security, and ethical aspects.</i></p>
<p>Other research outputs</p>	
<p>In addition to the management of data, are you also considering and planning for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout the projects?</p>	<p><i>Such outputs can be either digital (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g. new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.) Are those also following FAIR principles?</i></p> <p>We include in this category software, tools, workflows. We tried to address FAIR principles to the best extent possible (e.g., software and workflows history tracked on GitHub, provenance documents on yProv). We expect to publish software tools on open repositories (e.g., Zenodo).</p>
<p>Allocation of resources</p>	
<p>Who will be responsible for data management in your WP/Task?</p>	<p>All the partners involved in WP16/T16.3 (CMCC & UNITN).</p>
<p>How will long-term preservation be ensured?</p>	<p><i>(costs and potential value, who decides and how what data will be kept and for how long)</i></p> <p>Results are generated on demand by the applications, so this does not apply.</p>

Data Security	
What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?	Results are generated on demand by the applications, so this does not apply.
Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long-term preservation and curation?	Results are generated on demand by the applications, so this does not apply.
Ethical Aspects	
Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?	<i>Yes or No. (If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action DoA).</i> No
Will informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?	N/A
Other issues	
Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones?	<i>Please list and briefly describe them.</i> No

9.3. LifeWatch

Work Package	WP15/T15.2, WP16/T16.4
Contact	Lucia Vaira, Joaquin Lopez
Established a DMP, addressing important aspects of RDM.	In progress
Data Summary	
Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for?	LifeWatch ERIC does not directly host or provide data, but rather publishes metadata describing datasets, services, and other digital objects managed by its National Distributed Centres, and other external providers. In the EOSC Beyond context, LifeWatch ERIC reuses metadata records from its existing catalogue to demonstrate their federation and interoperability within EOSC. No existing metadata were discarded; representative records were selected for demonstrating integration with EOSC Core services
Will you re-use any existing data and will this generate new data?	No new data or metadata will be generated. The activity focuses on the technical federation of existing metadata records, without altering their content or creating new records.
What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reused: Metadata records (XML, JSON) following EML 2.2.0 and ISO19139 standards. • Generated: None.
What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?	To validate the interoperability and federation of the LifeWatch ERIC Metadata Catalogue with the EOSC Core components, enabling the discovery of LifeWatch metadata through the EOSC Discovery Hub.
What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?	Minimal (<500 MB), as only metadata records are handled.
What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?	Reused metadata comes from the existing LifeWatch ERIC Metadata Catalogue, which aggregates records contributed by LifeWatch National Distributed Centres, European projects, and external metadata providers.
To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?	To the EOSC and Research Infrastructure communities interested in catalogue and metadata federation and interoperability.
FAIR Data	
1.) Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	<i>Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?</i> Yes. Each metadata record maintains a persistent identifier.
	<i>Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.</i>

	<p>All metadata records are richly described and comply with ISO19139 and EML 2.2.0 standards.</p> <p><i>Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?</i></p> <p>Yes, all records already have lists of keywords.</p> <p><i>Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?</i></p> <p>Yes. Metadata will be harvested following the OAI-PMH protocol and indexed in the EOSC Discovery Hub.</p>
2.) Making data openly accessible	
a) Repository:	<p><i>Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?</i></p> <p>Yes, data will be stored in a trusted repository.</p> <p><i>Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?</i></p> <p>Metadata are stored and maintained within the LifeWatch ERIC Metadata Catalogue, which is a trusted platform based on GeoNetwork. LifeWatch does not host the actual datasets. Datasets used in the context of the user story belong to the LifeWatch Italy National Distributed Center and are deposited in a trusted repository that is the LifeWatch Italy Data Portal.</p> <p><i>Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?</i></p> <p>Each metadata record in the catalogue maintains a persistent identifier that uniquely identifies the described resource and resolves to its corresponding digital object.</p>
b) Data:	<p><i>Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.</i></p> <p>No primary data is hosted by LifeWatch ERIC. The catalogue provides access to metadata records that describe datasets and services managed by its National Distributed Centres and external providers. Each record includes the relevant links and access conditions as defined by the data/service owners. All metadata are published under a CC0 1.0 license, ensuring they are openly available, reusable, and accessible without restrictions.</p> <p><i>If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek the protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.</i></p> <p>Not applicable. LifeWatch ERIC does not host research data subject to embargoes or intellectual property restrictions. All metadata are made openly available upon publication in the catalogue.</p>

	<p><i>Will the data be accessible through a free and standardised access protocol?</i></p> <p>Yes. Metadata are accessible through free and standardised access protocols. In particular, the HTTPS (Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure) protocol is used.</p> <p><i>If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?</i></p> <p>No restrictions apply to the metadata managed by LifeWatch ERIC. All metadata are openly accessible and remain available beyond the end of the project. Any access restrictions apply only to the external resources described in the metadata and are defined by the original resource providers.</p> <p><i>How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?</i></p> <p>Metadata are openly accessible and do not require user authentication.</p> <p><i>Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?</i></p> <p>No. The LifeWatch ERIC Metadata Catalogue does not manage personal or sensitive data, and all metadata are openly accessible. Therefore, there is no need for a data access committee.</p>
<p>c) Metadata:</p>	<p><i>Will metadata be made openly available and licensed under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?</i></p> <p>Metadata are openly available and licensed under CC0 1.0, ensuring unrestricted discovery and reuse.</p> <p><i>How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?</i></p> <p>Metadata remains findable even if linked datasets are restricted or removed by the provider. However, to guarantee continuous quality check and improvement, decisions on metadata retention and curation are governed by LifeWatch's internal (meta)data management policies and carried out by the Service Centre team, which oversees catalogue operations.</p> <p><i>Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read or process the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open-source code)?</i></p> <p>No specific software is required to access or read the metadata, as all records are openly available through the LifeWatch ERIC Metadata Catalogue web interface and standard API endpoints. The catalogue itself is based on a customized version of GeoNetwork, an open-source platform, and technical documentation to the underlying software is publicly available.</p>

<p>3.) Making data interoperable</p>	<p><i>What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?</i></p> <p>LifeWatch ERIC ensures interoperability by adopting EML 2.2.0 and ISO 19139 metadata standards. For selected fields, the catalogue applies controlled vocabularies and semantic annotations to harmonise terminology and enable data discovery across domains. These practices follow community-endorsed interoperability principles, ensuring that metadata can be exchanged, harvested and reused within and beyond the biodiversity and environmental science communities.</p> <p><i>In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project-specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining, or extending them?</i></p> <p>No project-specific vocabularies or ontologies are expected to be created. However, if minor extensions are required to support EOSC federation, they will be documented, mapped to common ontologies and openly published via LifeWatch ERIC EcoPortal, which provides access to open, reusable vocabularies and ontologies.</p> <p><i>Will your data include qualified references to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?</i></p> <p>Yes. Each metadata record includes qualified references through persistent links to the original dataset, service or related resources.</p>
<p>4.) Increase data re-use</p>	<p><i>How will you provide the documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?</i></p> <p>In the case of services, such as the one developed in the EOSC Beyond user story (Analysis of alien species incidence across ecosystems), which consists of an R script, the corresponding metadata record provides detailed information on the methodology, inputs, processing steps, execution conditions and expected outputs.</p> <p>The datasets required for such services are described in their own metadata records, which include comprehensive information on variables, definitions and units of measurement. Together, these ensure that users can fully understand, validate and reuse the described resources.</p> <p><i>Will your data be made openly available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard re-use licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement? Under which license?</i></p> <p>LifeWatch ERIC does not produce or host datasets. However, all metadata records published through the LifeWatch ERIC Metadata Catalogue are openly available and released under a CC0 license, permitting unrestricted discovery and reuse.</p>

	<p><i>Will the data produced in the project be usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?</i></p> <p>In our case, the metadata will remain openly accessible and reusable by third parties beyond the end of the project, as they are preserved and maintained within the LifeWatch ERIC Metadata Catalogue, which ensures long-term availability through its operational infrastructure.</p> <p><i>Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?</i></p> <p>At the moment, LifeWatch ERIC does not use a metadata schema for describing the provenance of our metadata records.</p> <p><i>Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.</i></p> <p>Metadata quality is ensured through a combination of automated validation and manual curation.</p> <p>All records are checked for completeness and structural consistency in line with ISO 19139 and EML 2.2.0 standards. Each metadata record then goes through an editorial workflow, where a reviewer is assigned to evaluate the record's quality and provide feedback to the author before publication. Additional automated checks verify link functionality periodically.</p> <p>The Catalogue also integrates a FAIRness assessment tool, which evaluates the quality and completeness of metadata based on FAIR principles and provides feedback to further improve metadata records.</p> <p><i>Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security, and ethical aspects.</i></p>
Other research outputs	
<p>In addition to the management of data, are you also considering and planning for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout the projects?</p>	<p><i>Such outputs can be either digital (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g. new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.) Are those also following FAIR principles?</i></p> <p>LifeWatch ERIC manages the metadata describing various digital research outputs, including services, scripts, workflows, Virtual Research Environments, etc. The metadata records for those digital objects adhere to FAIR principles as well. LifeWatch does not plan to generate or reuse any additional research outputs beyond the metadata already published in its catalogue.</p>
Allocation of resources	
<p>Who will be responsible for data management in your WP/Task?</p>	<p>Lucia Vaira, LifeWatch ERIC Service Centre ICT Coordinator.</p>
<p>How will long-term preservation be ensured?</p>	<p><i>(costs and potential value, who decides and how what data will be kept and for how long)</i></p> <p>Long-term preservation of metadata is ensured through the LifeWatch ERIC Metadata Catalogue, which is a core, permanently maintained component of the LifeWatch ERIC infrastructure. As a European Research Infrastructure Consortium, LifeWatch ERIC guarantees the sustained hosting, maintenance, and accessibility of all published metadata</p>

	<p>records.</p> <p>Decisions on metadata retention and curation are governed by LifeWatch's internal (meta)data management policies and carried out by the Service Centre team, which oversees catalogue operations. In fact, the metadata descriptors are preserved to ensure continued access to essential information about digital objects, even in cases where the objects themselves may become unavailable.</p> <p>Since metadata represents a lasting reference to digital research outputs of long-term scientific value, their preservation is considered a permanent institutional responsibility with costs covered through LifeWatch ERIC's operational budget.</p>
Data Security	
What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?	<p>Data security is ensured through secure storage, regular backups, and a disaster recovery system that protects the LifeWatch ERIC Metadata Catalogue against data loss or system failure.</p> <p>The infrastructure is continuously monitored to prevent security breaches, and no sensitive or personal data are managed within the catalogue.</p>
Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long-term preservation and curation?	<p>Yes. All metadata are safely stored and curated within the LifeWatch ERIC Metadata Catalogue, a trusted repository managed and maintained by LifeWatch ERIC to ensure long-term preservation and accessibility.</p>
Ethical Aspects	
Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?	<p><i>Yes or No. (If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action DoA).</i></p> <p>No.</p> <p>(The LifeWatch ERIC Metadata Catalogue does not host or process personal, sensitive or confidential data. All metadata describe publicly available scientific resources and are shared under open licenses, so no ethical or legal issues are expected to impact data sharing.)</p>
Will informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?	<p>N/A.</p> <p>The LifeWatch ERIC Metadata Catalogue does not collect or process personal data, and therefore no informed consent procedures are required.</p>
Other issues	
Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/depart mental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones?	<p><i>Please list and briefly describe them.</i></p> <p>LifeWatch ERIC follows its own internal (meta)data management policies and procedures.</p>

9.4. METROFood-RI

Work Package	WP16/T16.5
Contact	Claudia Zoani, Karl Presser, Sara Seweryn
Established a DMP, addressing important aspects of RDM.	In progress
Data Summary	
Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for?	<p><i>State the reasons if re-use of any existing data has been considered but discarded.</i></p> <p>Yes, existing data will be re-used. We will process and handle the data submitted by users as part of the service ordering workflow, as well as the analytical results returned by laboratories. From these interactions, we will generate and store structured metadata describing the service request, its parameters, and its outcome. This metadata will be re-used to support service tracking, user access to results, and the overall operation of the platform. Only metadata will be exposed or reused; the detailed research data remain with the original providers and are not redistributed.</p>
Will you re-use any existing data and will this generate new data?	<p>Yes, we will re-use existing data. We will re-use the data provided by users during service requests, as well as the analytical results returned by laboratories, which may include various types of formats like CSV or Excel. These inputs will be processed to generate structured metadata describing the request, its parameters and its outcome. Yes, this process will generate new data in the form of operational and descriptive metadata that support service management and user access. The newly generated data do not include or redistribute the underlying research data.</p>
What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?	<p>The project will generate and re-use several types and formats of data. It will re-use data provided by users as part of service requests, as well as analytical results returned by laboratories in various formats like CSV, Excel, PDF, TXT and other structured files.</p>
What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?	<p>The purpose of the data generation and re-use is to support the full workflow of ordering, performing and delivering laboratory services. Re-used data from users and laboratories enable the platform to process service requests, track their progress and provide access to analytical results. The metadata generated by the project help structure, classify and describe each service interaction, improving usability, transparency and traceability.</p>
What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?	<p>The expected size of the data that the project will generate or re-use is relatively moderate. Different datasets vary in volume depending on their type and origin. Descriptive and reference datasets—such as analytes descriptions, food contamination data, reference materials, thesauri and infrastructure data—are expected to range between 0.10 and 0.50 GB, with some larger reference collections reaching up to 1.00 GB. Service-related data and analytical outputs, including results from electron microscopy or specific</p>

	food processing studies, are expected to be around 0.10 GB each. Overall, the total data volume will consist of multiple small to medium datasets, amounting to a manageable combined size.
What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?	The data generated or re-used in the project originate from several well-defined sources. Re-used data come from users who submit information and materials when requesting laboratory services, as well as from laboratories that return analytical results in various structured formats.
To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?	The data produced by the project may be useful to a wide range of stakeholders beyond the project itself. Metadata describing laboratory services, analytical capabilities and research outputs can support other research infrastructures, private laboratories and academic groups seeking comparable services or reference information. Food industry actors—such as producers, quality-control teams and R&D departments—may benefit from improved visibility of available analytical services and reference materials.
FAIR Data	
1.) Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	<i>Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?</i>
	Yes , the data will be identified by persistent identifiers where appropriate.
	<i>Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.</i>
	Yes , rich metadata will be provided to support discovery. The platform generates EOSC-compliant metadata for each service, including descriptions, scientific domains, categories, access conditions, geographic availability, contacts, policies and additional contextual information.
	<i>Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?</i>
	Yes , search keywords will be included in the metadata to improve discovery and potential re-use. Keywords are provided through fields such as tags, categories, scientific domains, and target user groups, all mapped to controlled vocabularies to ensure consistent indexing.
	<i>Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?</i>
	Yes . Metadata will be indexed in the EOSC Discovery Hub.
2.) Making data openly accessible	
a) Repository:	<i>Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?</i>
	Yes , the data will be deposited in a trusted repository where appropriate.

	<p><i>Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?</i></p> <p><i>Metadata are stored and maintained within the Metrofood Catalogue, which is a trusted platform with databases and IT infrastructure self hosted by Metrofood partner - Premotec.</i></p> <p><i>Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?</i></p> <p>Yes, each metadata record in the catalogue is assigned a persistent identifier that uniquely identifies the resource and reliably resolves to its corresponding digital object.</p>
b) Data:	<p><i>Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.</i></p> <p>The catalogue provides access only to metadata records that describe services and the associated datasets managed by the participating facilities and external service providers. Each metadata record includes links and access conditions defined by the respective data or service owner.</p> <p><i>If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek the protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.</i></p> <p>N/A</p> <p><i>Will the data be accessible through a free and standardised access protocol?</i></p> <p>Yes, the metadata will be accessible through a free and standardised access protocol. Service-level metadata is exposed through the catalogue infrastructure, which provides open, protocol-based access to records (e.g., HTTPS/REST).</p> <p><i>If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?</i></p> <p>Access to restricted data will be provided only to authorised users through controlled, service-specific workflows.</p> <p><i>How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?</i></p> <p>The identity of each person accessing restricted data will be verified through the platform's authentication and authorisation system integrated with EOSC.</p> <p><i>Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?</i></p> <p>No, there is no need for a data access committee. The platform does not host or distribute primary analytical data, and access to</p>

	restricted datasets is handled directly by the facilities providing the service.
c) Metadata:	<p><i>Will metadata be made openly available and licensed under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?</i></p> <p>Yes, the metadata will be made openly available and released under a public domain dedication such as CC0, in line with the Grant Agreement.</p> <p><i>How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?</i></p> <p>The metadata will remain available and findable for the long term through the catalogue infrastructure. Service-level metadata will continue to be accessible even if the underlying analytical data are no longer available, ensuring persistent discovery and referencing of the service.</p> <p><i>Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read or process the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open-source code)?</i></p> <p>No specialised software is required to access or read the metadata, so no additional documentation is needed. The metadata are provided in standard, widely supported formats and can be accessed through common web protocols.</p>
3.) Making data interoperable	<p><i>What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?</i></p> <p>The project follows EOSC Catalogue & Marketplace metadata standards and controlled vocabularies to ensure interoperability across services and disciplines. Data and metadata use standard formats such as JSON, CSV, Excel, and PDF, while scientific domains, categories, access conditions and other descriptors are mapped through a crosswalk to community-endorsed EOSC vocabularies.</p> <p><i>In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project-specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining, or extending them?</i></p> <p>Yes, if project-specific vocabularies are required, we will provide mappings to commonly used EOSC and community ontologies. Any internally curated vocabularies used for service descriptions will be aligned through the crosswalk mechanism and openly published to ensure they can be reused, refined or extended by others.</p>

	<p><i>Will your data include qualified references to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?</i></p> <p>Yes, the metadata will include qualified references to other relevant resources where applicable. These may include links to related services, reference materials, external datasets, or supporting documentation provided by laboratories or previous research activities.</p>
<p>4.) Increase data re-use</p>	<p><i>How will you provide the documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?</i></p> <p>N/A</p> <p><i>Will your data be made openly available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard re-use licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement? Under which license?</i></p> <p><u>Yes, the metadata will be made openly available in the public domain to permit the widest possible re-use. They will be released under a standard open licence such as CC0.</u></p> <p><i>Will the data produced in the project be usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?</i></p> <p>Yes, the metadata will remain accessible in the Metrofood-RI Catalogue.</p> <p><i>Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?</i></p> <p>Yes, the provenance of the data will be thoroughly documented. The metadata records include information about the service provider, data origin, update history and relevant identifiers, ensuring full traceability</p> <p><i>Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.</i></p> <p>Data quality is ensured through several complementary processes. All metadata are generated via a controlled mapping from validated internal service records to the EOSC-compliant schema, ensuring structural and semantic consistency. Mandatory fields, controlled vocabularies and validation rules prevent incomplete or inconsistent entries. Laboratories are responsible for the accuracy of their service descriptions and methodological information, while the platform performs automated checks and periodic reviews to maintain correctness, completeness and up-to-date metadata.</p> <p><i>Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security, and ethical aspects.</i></p>
<p>Other research outputs</p>	

<p>In addition to the management of data, are you also considering and planning for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout the projects?</p>	<p><i>Such outputs can be either digital (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g. new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.) Are those also following FAIR principles?</i></p> <p>Yes, other research outputs generated or re-used in the project are also considered, particularly digital outputs such as software components, workflows, mappings, and controlled vocabularies used in the catalogue. These outputs follow FAIR principles where applicable: they are documented, versioned, use persistent identifiers where needed, and rely on open or widely adopted standards. Physical outputs such as laboratory samples or materials remain under the responsibility of the providing laboratories and therefore cannot be fully FAIRified, but their associated metadata and protocols are described in the catalogue to support transparency and reuse.</p>
<p>Allocation of resources</p>	
<p>Who will be responsible for data management in your WP/Task?</p>	<p>Data management in this Work Package/Task will be the responsibility of the team maintaining the catalogue (PREMOTEC / METROFOOD) and EOSC integration layer. This includes the technical lead overseeing metadata generation and quality, as well as the platform administrators responsible for ensuring compliance with FAIR principles, security, and long-term availability of the service-level metadata.</p>
<p>How will long-term preservation be ensured?</p>	<p><i>(costs and potential value, who decides and how what data will be kept and for how long)</i></p> <p>Long-term preservation will be ensured through the EOSC-compliant catalogue infrastructure, which stores service-level metadata independently of the lifecycle of individual datasets. Since only metadata are preserved (not primary analytical data), the costs remain low and are covered as part of the platform's ongoing maintenance.</p>
<p>Data Security</p>	
<p>What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?</p>	<p>Data security is ensured through secure storage, controlled access and reliable recovery mechanisms. Service-level metadata are stored within a protected Catalogue infrastructure with regular backups and disaster-recovery procedures. Sensitive data exchanged between users and laboratories—such as files submitted for analysis or returned results—are transferred over encrypted channels and accessed only via the EOSC authentication and authorisation system.</p>
<p>Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long-term preservation and curation?</p>	<p>Yes, the data will be safely stored in trusted repositories for long-term preservation and curation. Service-level metadata are preserved within a catalogue infrastructure, which provides stable storage, regular backups and long-term accessibility. Primary analytical data are not stored on the platform; they remain securely managed and preserved by the laboratories according to their own trusted institutional policies.</p>
<p>Ethical Aspects</p>	
<p>Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?</p>	<p><i>Yes or No. (If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action DoA).</i></p> <p>No</p>

<p>Will informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?</p>	<p>Yes, informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation will be included whenever personal data are collected. Users submitting personal information during the service request process will be informed about how their data are processed, who can access them, and how long they are retained, in accordance with GDPR requirements.</p>
<p>Other issues</p>	
<p>Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones?</p>	<p><i>Please list and briefly describe them.</i></p> <p>N/A</p>

9.5. NI4OS

Work Package	WP16/T16.6
Contact	Anastas Mishev, Dusan Vudragovic
Established a DMP, addressing important aspects of RDM.	In place
Data Summary	
Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for?	<p><i>State the reasons if re-use of any existing data has been considered but discarded.</i></p> <p>Yes, information about the initial set of services and repositories collected during the NI4OS-Europe project.</p>
Will you re-use any existing data and will this generate new data?	Yes, we will update the initial dataset to align with the development of EOSC resource profiles.
What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?	All collected information will be stored within the NI4OS-Europe catalog according to the formats specified by the catalog technology. We are using the catalog provided by the EOSC Beyond project. Additionally, the catalog gathers information about the service owners and their institutions.
What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?	The purpose of generating or reusing data is to support the project's research and technical objectives by ensuring that all outputs are FAIR, interoperable, and reusable by the wider research community.
What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?	The expected data size does not exceed a few tenths of a megabyte.
What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?	All information is entered into the system by registered service providers and managed by the NI4OS-Europe operational team.
To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?	Regional researchers, researchers from Europe, and the broader EOSC community.
FAIR Data	
1.) Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	<i>Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?</i>
	Each catalog entry is assigned a unique and persistent ID.
	<i>Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.</i>
	All entries will be described according to the latest EOSC resource profiles metadata schemas.

	<p><i>Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?</i></p> <p>Yes</p> <p><i>Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?</i></p> <p>Yes</p>
2.) Making data openly accessible	
a) Repository:	<p><i>Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?</i></p> <p>The repository is maintained within the NI4OS-Europe community.</p> <p><i>Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?</i></p> <p>It is currently maintained on a best effort basis.</p> <p><i>Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?</i></p> <p>Yes, that is already the case.</p>
b) Data:	<p><i>Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.</i></p> <p>Information relevant to the EOSC ecosystem will be openly accessible. However, some details, such as service provider email addresses, will remain private. Support and security channels, on the other hand, are publicly available.</p> <p><i>If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek the protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.</i></p> <p>N/A</p> <p><i>Will the data be accessible through a free and standardised access protocol?</i></p> <p>Yes</p> <p><i>If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?</i></p> <p>No restrictions</p> <p><i>How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?</i></p> <p>The catalog is completely integrated with the AAI system, so every request must be authenticated.</p>

	<p><i>Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?</i></p> <p>No need.</p>
c) Metadata:	<p><i>Will metadata be made openly available and licensed under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?</i></p> <p>Yes</p> <p><i>How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?</i></p> <p>Both metadata and data will be available via the portal and API. If interest in maintaining the NI4OS-Europe node decreases, all data will be exported and stored in a publicly accessible repository.</p> <p><i>Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read or process the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open-source code)?</i></p> <p>No special software is required; all information can be accessed via a REST-based API.</p>
3.) Making data interoperable	<p><i>What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?</i></p> <p>EOSC resource profiles</p> <p><i>In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project-specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining, or extending them?</i></p> <p>Currently, there is no need to alter the existing ontologies or vocabularies. If any extensions to the used vocabulary become necessary, these will be documented.</p> <p><i>Will your data include qualified references to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?</i></p> <p>Yes, some data are interconnected or have external references.</p>
4.) Increase data re-use	<p><i>How will you provide the documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?</i></p> <p>We will prepare the relevant documentation and also attempt to validate data automatically through the monitoring system.</p> <p><i>Will your data be made openly available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard re-use licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement? Under which license?</i></p>

	<p>Access to the full set of information access authentication is required. However, some subsets of the information are available in the public domain.</p> <p><i>Will the data produced in the project be usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?</i></p> <p>We will ensure that data can be reused, but we cannot guarantee it will actually happen.</p> <p><i>Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?</i></p> <p>Information about the person who entered data into the system is stored together with the data.</p> <p><i>Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.</i></p> <p>Currently, information is stored using dedicated input forms that perform basic validation checks—for example, verifying data types such as strings, numbers, dates, and email formats—and ensuring that all mandatory fields are completed before submission. These forms provide a minimal level of data quality control, preventing incomplete or improperly formatted entries from being saved.</p> <p><i>Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security, and ethical aspects.</i></p> <p>We are aware of this, but currently, we haven't implemented those aspects.</p>
Other research outputs	
<p>In addition to the management of data, are you also considering and planning for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout the projects?</p>	<p><i>Such outputs can be either digital (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g. new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.) Are those also following FAIR principles?</i></p> <p>We intend to extend the current set of objects by adding more software and workflows, all developed following the same principles. Therefore, we can also consider these to be FAIR.</p>
Allocation of resources	
<p>Who will be responsible for data management in your WP/Task?</p>	<p>We have formed an onboarding team responsible for data management as well.</p>
<p>How will long-term preservation be ensured?</p>	<p><i>(costs and potential value, who decides and how what data will be kept and for how long)</i></p> <p>The individual who entered data into the system can delete it. The onboarding team can hide data if it is inappropriate or outdated, but they are not permitted to delete it.</p>
Data Security	

What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?	The system connects to the AAI, necessitating user authentication and authorization. All servers, databases, and cloud platforms employ full-disk encryption and encrypted backup volumes. Both internal and external data transfers occur over secure channels such as SSH and HTTPS. Processing personal data aligns with GDPR requirements, with oversight from Data Protection Officers.
Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long-term preservation and curation?	Yes, if interest in maintaining the NI4OS-Europe node decreases, all data will be exported and stored in a trusted publicly accessible repository for long-term preservation.
Ethical Aspects	
Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?	<i>Yes or No. (If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action DoA).</i> No
Will informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?	Yes
Other issues	
Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departamental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones?	The organization responsible for hosting the catalog follows established institutional procedures for data management that are aligned with national requirements. These procedures are designed to ensure proper handling, security, and compliance of data at every level of operation, thereby promoting consistency and reliability in data management practices. Additionally, the organization adheres to relevant EU regulations to maintain regulatory compliance and support interoperability within the European data framework.

9.6. e-INFRA CZ

Work Package	WP16/T16.7
Contact	Zdenek Sustr, Miroslav Ruda
Established a DMP, addressing important aspects of RDM.	In place
Data Summary	
Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for?	The infrastructure is fully operational and its data handling policies are already in place. The data are mainly personal data of users, which are handled in compliance with GDPR, and configuration data for services, which are handled in compliance with service management and information security principles.
Will you re-use any existing data and will this generate new data?	A routine turnover of data is expected
What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?	The data are mainly personal data of users and configuration data for services.
What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?	User access and customization, service management.
What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?	N/A, low amount, highly distributed.
What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?	Filled in by humans.
To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?	Hackers, blackmailers, cyber criminals.
FAIR Data	
1.) Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	<i>Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?</i>
	No
	<i>Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.</i>
	No
	<i>Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?</i>

	No
	<i>Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?</i>
	No
2.) Making data openly accessible	
a) Repository:	<i>Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?</i>
	Yes
	<i>Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?</i>
	Yes
	<i>Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?</i>
	No
b) Data:	<i>Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.</i>
	No
	<i>If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek the protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.</i>
	N/A
	<i>Will the data be accessible through a free and standardised access protocol?</i>
	No
	<i>If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?</i>
	Access Control
	<i>How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?</i>
	In compliance with GDPR
	<i>Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?</i>
	No

c) Metadata:	<p><i>Will metadata be made openly available and licensed under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?</i></p> <p>No</p>
	<p><i>How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?</i></p> <p>N/A</p>
	<p><i>Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read or process the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open-source code)?</i></p> <p>N/A</p>
3.) Making data interoperable	<p><i>What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?</i></p> <p>OIDC</p>
	<p><i>In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project-specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining, or extending them?</i></p> <p>Yes</p>
	<p><i>Will your data include qualified references to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?</i></p> <p>Not sure</p>
4.) Increase data re-use	<p><i>How will you provide the documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?</i></p> <p>No</p>
	<p><i>Will your data be made openly available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard re-use licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement? Under which license?</i></p> <p>No</p>
	<p><i>Will the data produced in the project be usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?</i></p> <p>No</p>
	<p><i>Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?</i></p> <p>Yes</p>

	Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes. N/A Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security, and ethical aspects.
Other research outputs	
In addition to the management of data, are you also considering and planning for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout the projects?	Such outputs can be either digital (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g. new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.) Are those also following FAIR principles? Yes, management of resulting services is a major focus.
Allocation of resources	
Who will be responsible for data management in your WP/Task?	Individual service owners, and roles appointed under GDPR.
How will long-term preservation be ensured?	(costs and potential value, who decides and how what data will be kept and for how long) In accordance with GDPR and ITSM
Data Security	
What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?	Governed by ISMS, in place and certified (ISO/IEC 27001:2023).
Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long-term preservation and curation?	Yes, where applicable under ISMS and GDPR.
Ethical Aspects	
Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?	Yes or No. (If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action DoA). Yes
Will informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?	N/A, there will be no such questionnaires.
Other issues	

Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones?	<i>Please list and briefly describe them.</i> No, all in place already.
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9.7. NFDI

Work Package	WP16/T16.8
Contact	Tim Wetzel, Sander Apweiler, Marvin Winkens, York Sure-Vetter
Established a DMP, addressing important aspects of RDM.	In place
Data Summary	
Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for?	Yes, data from (mainly) photon science experiments will be re-used as part of our use case stories and demonstrations in WP15 & 16 as well as for potential integration tests with adapters in WP 12. Re-use with the knowledge graph is foreseen, too.
Will you re-use any existing data and will this generate new data?	Yes, existing data will be re-used and we also expect to generate new data if use cases permit.
What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?	Mostly scientific data from experiments in the specific formats used (ORSO, NeXuS, hdf5, tiff & similar) as well as metadata (JSON, XML, txt, md & similarly descriptive formats)
What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?	The data generated will either be necessary to demonstrate the success of testing during use cases and scientific user stories or a result of that.
What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?	<10 GB
What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?	Datasets from scientific experiments (mainly photon science facilities) and the rich descriptive metadata needed to describe them.
To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?	Photon scientists who want to re-use the published datasets for their own work.
FAIR Data	
1.) Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	<p><i>Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?</i></p> <p>Yes, in any case by a catalog-specific UUID if the data is not published elsewhere or a DOI that can be generated by users after ingesting their dataset into the catalog.</p> <p><i>Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.</i></p> <p>Yes. It will be available in the DataCite schema via OAI-PMH and community- and/or experiment-specific additions are allowed in addition to bibliographic metadata in the catalog itself.</p>

	<p><i>Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?</i></p> <p>Yes</p> <p><i>Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?</i></p> <p>Yes</p>
2.) Making data openly accessible	
a) Repository:	<p><i>Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?</i></p> <p>Yes, https://public-data.desy.de</p> <p><i>Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?</i></p> <p>Yes</p> <p><i>Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?</i></p> <p>Yes/Yes</p>
b) Data:	<p><i>Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.</i></p> <p>Yes (in the case of public-data.desy.de)</p> <p><i>If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek the protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.</i></p> <p><i>Will the data be accessible through a free and standardised access protocol?</i></p> <p>Yes</p> <p><i>If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?</i></p> <p>Data is stored in a storage system that is provided independently of the project.</p> <p><i>How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?</i></p> <p>Anonymous access is possible as well as authenticated login through eduGAIN, EOSC-AAI, IAM4NFDI, HelmholtzID</p> <p><i>Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?</i></p> <p>No, the data is public and non-sensitive</p>

<p>c) Metadata:</p>	<p><i>Will metadata be made openly available and licensed under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?</i></p> <p>Yes and yes</p> <hr/> <p><i>How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?</i></p> <p>Yes, indefinitely as of now.</p> <hr/> <p><i>Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read or process the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open-source code)?</i></p> <p>Yes, inclusion is possible but subject to the submitter's discretion.</p>
<p>3.) Making data interoperable</p>	<p><i>What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?</i></p> <p>DataCite, OAI-PMH, own metadata schemata defined as JSON-Schema or similar</p> <hr/> <p><i>In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project-specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining, or extending them?</i></p> <p>Yes, mappings are subject to the creator's discretion</p> <hr/> <p><i>Will your data include qualified references to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?</i></p> <p>Yes, as per the standards for good scientific practice</p>
<p>4.) Increase data re-use</p>	<p><i>How will you provide the documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?</i></p> <p>Dataset submitters are encouraged to include at least a readme-file to document, or better, a jupyter-notebook to demonstrate usage of the data. During data curation, this aspect is emphasized.</p> <hr/> <p><i>Will your data be made openly available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard re-use licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement? Under which license?</i></p> <p>Yes, either CC-0 or CC-BY4.0 at the discretion of dataset owners/submitters</p> <hr/> <p><i>Will the data produced in the project be usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?</i></p> <p>Yes</p>

	<p><i>Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?</i></p> <p>Yes</p> <p><i>Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.</i></p> <p>Data will need to be described by rich metadata according to a pre-defined metadata schema and it will be curated by a community-appointed data curator. Data will be stored on a system that ensures data retention according to standards.</p> <p><i>Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security, and ethical aspects.</i></p>
Other research outputs	
<p>In addition to the management of data, are you also considering and planning for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout the projects?</p>	<p><i>Such outputs can be either digital (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g. new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.) Are those also following FAIR principles?</i></p> <p>Not yet but possible in the future.</p>
Allocation of resources	
<p>Who will be responsible for data management in your WP/Task?</p>	<p>Tim Wetzel for public-data.desy.de</p>
<p>How will long-term preservation be ensured?</p>	<p><i>(costs and potential value, who decides and how what data will be kept and for how long)</i></p> <p>Data is stored on a system that is available to the scientific community through other channels as well and is financed independently of project work.</p>
Data Security	
<p>What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?</p>	<p>Data is stored via dCache on disk and tape simultaneously for data security and safety reasons. dCache is a storage system in use by several institutions mainly in the high-energy physics community and adheres to best practices and standards of WLCG.</p>
<p>Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long-term preservation and curation?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
Ethical Aspects	
<p>Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?</p>	<p><i>Yes or No. (If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action DoA).</i></p> <p>There are no ethical aspects we are currently aware of.</p>

Will informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?	Yes, submitters of data have to acknowledge that their name and email address are stored and published with their datasets to ensure provenance information is available.
Other issues	
Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones?	<i>Please list and briefly describe them.</i> Yes, data management is also ensured through inclusion in Helmholtz- and NFDI-related activities in Germany.

9.8. CESSDA

Work Package	WP 15
Contact	John Sheperdson
Established a DMP, addressing important aspects of RDM.	Not applicable

9.9. CNB-CSIC

Work Package	WP15/T15.2, WP16/T16.2
Contact	Irene Sanchez Lopez, Carlos Oscar, Jose Maria Carazo
Established a DMP, addressing important aspects of RDM.	In progress
Data Summary	
Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for?	<p><i>State the reasons if re-use of any existing data has been considered but discarded.</i></p> <p>One of the use cases that will be implemented through this Pilot Node will validate existing structures deposited in public databases. This data, consisting of volumes and atomic models, will be taken from the Electron Microscopy Data Bank (EMDB) and the Protein Data Bank (PDB) respectively.</p>
Will you re-use any existing data and will this generate new data?	<p>The workflow will start from volumes and atomic models and the data processing pipeline will create a Scipion (https://scipion.i2pc.es/) project and new outputs such as: CTFs, coordinates, particles and volumes.</p> <p>Apart from this, this use case will use/create other kinds of data: container-related files and TOSCA files used for deployment orchestration.</p>
What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?	<p>Data will consist mainly of micrographs, CTFs, coordinates, particles, 2d classes, volumes, 3d classes and data processing pipelines. The formats are basically .tiff, .psd, .xmd, .png, .txt, .stk, .pos, .mrc, .mrsc, .vol, .star, .json, .sqlite</p> <p>The container-related files formats are .def and .sif and the TOSCA files .yaml</p>
What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?	<p>The purpose of re-using existing public data is to validate the quality of it and to test the workflow pipeline and check if we can achieve good results. The purpose of generating new data is to use the workflow for processing volumes and atomic models recently resolved by CryoEM researchers.</p> <p>The goal of using container images is to set up the software in the machine and the TOSCA recipes to deploy these machines in the cloud.</p>
What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?	<p>CryoEM volumes and atomic models are not that big, in the order of hundred megabytes. The size of the rest of the Scipion project altogether with the remaining outputs would seize less than 10 GiB.</p> <p>Container image size is less than 50 GiB and TOSCA files are small, of few megabytes.</p>
What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?	<p>Public data will come from EMDB (https://www.ebi.ac.uk/emdb/) and PDB (https://www.ebi.ac.uk/pdbe/). New data will come from CryoEM researchers labs.</p> <p>Scipion container recipes are placed at https://github.com/I2PC/scipion-containers/ and the images are available at rinchen.cnb.csic.es (and can be downloaded with</p>

	<p>the aptainer command "aptainer pull oras://rinchen.cnb.csic.es/scipion/\$container-name").</p> <p>TOSCA recipes can be found at https://github.com/grycap/tosca</p>	
To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?	To the whole structural biology community, CryoEM facilities, research institutes, pharmaceutical companies, etc.	
FAIR Data		
1.) Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	<p><i>Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?</i></p> <p>Re-used data yes, because we will use volumes and atomic models from EMDB and PDB entries. Let's say we use the volume of EMD-42836, this entry has the DOI https://www.ebi.ac.uk/emdb/EMD-42836 and its related atomic model 8tqo has the DOI https://www.ebi.ac.uk/pdbe/entry/pdb/8tqo</p> <p>New raw data won't have a persistent identifier unless the researcher is happy enough with the quality of it and it ends in EMDB and PDB.</p>	
	<p><i>Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.</i></p> <p>Don't think so.</p>	
	<p><i>Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?</i></p> <p>Don't think so.</p>	
	<p><i>Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?</i></p> <p>N/A</p>	
	2.) Making data openly accessible	
	a) Repository:	<p><i>Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?</i></p> <p>As it is said before, if the authors achieve a good volume, at some point it will be published at EMDB and the atomic model data at PDB. Both of them are the standard repositories used for deposit Electron Microscopy data, so yes, they are trusted repositories.</p>
<p><i>Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?</i></p> <p>There is no need to create arrangements with the repositories, this is the standard procedure in Electron Microscopy.</p>		
<p><i>Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?</i></p> <p>Yes, both EMDB and PDB.</p>		

<p>b) Data:</p>	<p><i>Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.</i></p> <p>It depends if the data processing pipeline ends in a good result or not. If the volume obtained is good enough, it will be eventually published at EMDB and the atomic model at PDB. However, if the data processing outcome is unsatisfactory, the data may not be published anywhere.</p> <p><i>If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek the protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.</i></p> <p>N/A</p> <p><i>Will the data be accessible through a free and standardised access protocol?</i></p> <p>If the data is published at EMDB and PDB, yes. EMDB volumes and PDB atomic models are relatively small and can be downloaded with HTTPS protocol.</p> <p><i>If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?</i></p> <p>Data published at EMDB and PDB can be accessed without restrictions.</p> <p><i>How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?</i></p> <p>There is no login system at EMDB or PDB and there is no need for having it, so people won't be identified.</p> <p><i>Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?</i></p> <p>No</p>
<p>c) Metadata:</p>	<p><i>Will metadata be made openly available and licensed under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?</i></p> <p>Yes, the metadata for EMDB entries are openly available at https://www.ebi.ac.uk/emdb/api/entry/EMD-XXXXX (where XXXX is the entry id). For PDB is the same, it can be retrieved from https://www.ebi.ac.uk/pdbe/api/pdb/entry/summary/XXXX</p> <p>This metadata contains references to the DOI or the entry id, so yes, it will enable the user to access it.</p> <p><i>How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?</i></p> <p>EMDB and PDBe are owned by the EMBL-EBI, a well established research organization funded by several member and associate</p>

	<p>states. So it's difficult for them to lose the funding for maintaining these repositories, so the data will be available and findable hopefully forever.</p> <p><i>Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read or process the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open-source code)?</i></p> <p>Yes, the EMDB entry describes which software has been used for the data processing (such as Scipion, Relion, Cryosparc, etc.).</p>
<p>3.) Making data interoperable</p>	<p><i>What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?</i></p> <p>N/A</p> <p><i>In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project-specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining, or extending them?</i></p> <p>N/A</p> <p><i>Will your data include qualified references to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?</i></p> <p>No, each data processing pipeline will start from scratch with volumes/atomic models and won't use any other existing data.</p>
<p>4.) Increase data re-use</p>	<p><i>How will you provide the documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?</i></p> <p>Scipion projects are designed to be reusable, so anyone can reproduce the analysis having the JSON workflow file and the input data.</p> <p><i>Will your data be made openly available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard re-use licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement? Under which license?</i></p> <p>If a publication is achieved, for sure volumes will be openly available at EMDB under CC0 license.</p> <p><i>Will the data produced in the project be usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?</i></p> <p>Could be. The resolved 3D structures could be used for any biological study afterwards.</p> <p><i>Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?</i></p> <p>Don't think so.</p> <p><i>Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.</i></p> <p>The whole Validation Report Service, the software this Pilot Node is based on, assesses the quality of the CryoEM data provided by the user, such as the volume and the atomic model.</p>

	Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security, and ethical aspects.
1.) Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	<p>Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?</p> <p>Re-used data yes, because we will use volumes and atomic models from EMDB and PDB entries. Let's say we use the volume of EMD-42836, this entry has the DOI https://www.ebi.ac.uk/emdb/EMD-42836 and its related atomic model 8tqo has the DOI https://www.ebi.ac.uk/pdbe/entry/pdb/8tqo</p> <p>New raw data won't have a persistent identifier unless the researcher is happy enough with the quality of it and it ends in EMDB and PDB.</p>
Other research outputs	
In addition to the management of data, are you also considering and planning for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout the projects?	<p>Such outputs can be either digital (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g. new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.) Are those also following FAIR principles?</p> <p>Yes, apart from the CryoEM data there will be workflows, containers, recipes and images and TOSCA files, as they were described before. All of them will be placed in a trusted repository so they can be re-used: container recipes at Github (https://github.com/I2PC/scipion-containers/), container images at rinchen.cnb.csic.es and TOSCA recipes at https://github.com/grycap/tosca</p>
Allocation of resources	
Who will be responsible for data management in your WP/Task?	Irene Sánchez López, Carlos Oscar Sorzano and José María Carazo
How will long-term preservation be ensured?	<p>(costs and potential value, who decides and how what data will be kept and for how long)</p> <p>Research outputs (, container recipes and TOSCA recipes) are in public repositories so as long as the Github project is alive, there will be available.</p> <p>For the data published at EMDB and PDB and it was said before, the previous statement applies here, depending on EMBL-EBI.</p>
Data Security	
What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?	Non-public volumes or atomic models from users will be transferred to the cloud machine where they will be processed with Scipion using a secure method or protocol such as rsync or GridFTP.
Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long-term preservation and curation?	For the data published, we imagine EMDB and PDB have data security policies implemented.

Ethical Aspects	
Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?	Yes or No. (If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action DoA). No
Will informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?	N/A
Other issues	
Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/depart mental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones?	Please list and briefly describe them. No

Annex A. Privacy Policy

With this privacy policy we, The EGI Foundation, inform the project members about which personal data is collected and processed when using EGI Collaboration Tools. Table 3 outlines the complete policy.

Name of the Service	Collaboration tools for the EOSC Beyond project
Description of the Service	<p>The EGI Collaboration Tools services for the EOSC Beyond (hereinafter referred to as: "the service" or "Collaboration Tools") support the EOSC Beyond project's activities. Personal data is used to provide access to the service with the proper access levels. Personal data is collected as part of the project's activities.</p> <p>This privacy notice describes how we, the EGI Foundation (hereinafter referred to as "we" or "the Data Controller"), collect and process data by which project members can be personally identified ("Personal Data") when the service is used.</p>
Data controller	The EGI Foundation , Science Park 140, 1098 XG Amsterdam, The Netherlands.
Data protection officer	The EGI Foundation , Data Protection Officer, Science Park 140, 1098 XG Amsterdam, The Netherlands, E-mail: dpo@egi.eu
Jurisdiction and supervisory authority	<p>Jurisdiction: NL, The Netherlands</p> <p>EGI Foundation's lead supervisory authority is the Dutch Data Protection Authority. They can be contacted at https://autoriteitpersoonsgegevens.nl/en/contact-dutch-dpa/contact-us</p>
Personal data processed	<p>The service may process the following personal data:</p> <p>Identification data: Name, Identification number, E-mail address, Phone number, Address, Bank details, Other: affiliation, IP address</p> <p>Behavioural data: Usage data, Data on purchase or payment transactions, Working time data, Other: technical logs with timestamps, attendance at meetings</p> <p>Data allowing conclusions on the personality: Other: membership information on groups, roles, and communities</p> <p>Biographical data: CV data</p> <p>Sociodemographic data: Gender</p>

Purpose of the processing of personal data	<p>The purpose of the collection, processing, and use of the personal data mentioned above is:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To provide the service functions, to coordinate and manage the project according to applicable requirements including projects' contracts, guidelines, funding policies, and legal requirements. • To keep evidence for audit needs. • To monitor and maintain service stability, performance, and security.
Legal basis	<p>The legal basis for processing personal data is compliance with a legal obligation or legitimate interests pursued by the controller or by a third party according to Art. 6 (1) (f) General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).</p>
Third parties to whom personal data is disclosed	<p>Personal data will not be used beyond the original purpose of their acquisition. If forwarding to third parties should be necessary to answer an inquiry or to carry out a service, the consent of the data subject is considered to have been given by entering a contract when using the respective function or service. In particular, the data provided will not be used for advertising purposes.</p> <p>For the purpose given in this privacy policy, personal data may be passed to the following third parties:</p> <p>Within the European Union (EU) / European Economic Area (EEA):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CESNET: resource provider, sub-contracted data processor of EGI Foundation • Google Ireland Limited: resource provider, sub-contracted data processor of EGI Foundation • Zenodo: public deliverables and publications • European Commission • Project's partners • Individuals responsible for managing projects, Work Packages, and tasks. • The records of your use and technical log files produced by the service components may be shared for security incident response purposes with other authorised participants in the academic and research-distributed digital infrastructures via secured mechanisms, only for the same purposes and only as far as necessary to provide the incident response capability were doing so is likely to assist in the investigation of suspected misuse of Infrastructure resources. <p>Outside the EU / EEA:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project's partners • Individuals responsible for managing projects, Work Packages, and tasks. <p>Any data transfer to a third country outside the EU or the EEA only takes place under the conditions contained in Chapter V of the GDPR and in compliance with the provisions of this privacy policy and any related policies adopted by the EGI Federation.</p>

Your rights	<p>You can exercise the following rights at any time by contacting our Data Protection Officer using the contact details provided in the Data Protection Officer section:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Information about the data stored with us and their processing ● Correction of incorrect personal data ● Deletion of the data stored by us ● Restriction of data processing, if we are not yet allowed to delete the data due to legal obligations ● Objection to the processing of the data by us ● Data portability <p>Project members can complain at any time to the supervisory data protection authority (DPA). The responsible DPA depends on the country and state of residence, of the project member's workplace, or of the presumed violation. A list of the supervisory authorities with addresses can be found at https://edpb.europa.eu/about-edpb/board/members_en.</p> <p>You can contact EGI Foundation's lead supervising authority using the contact details provided in the Jurisdiction and Supervisory Authority section.</p>
Data retention and deletion	<p>As per EC Grant agreements' requirements, data should be kept for at least 5 years after the end of the project.</p> <p>The data are deleted or anonymised as soon as retention periods have passed, and the data are not required anymore for any of the purposes listed above.</p> <p>The records of the project members' use and technical log files produced by the service components will be deleted or anonymised after, at most, 18 months as documented in EGI-doc 2732: Policy on the Processing of Personal Data.</p>
Security	<p>We take appropriate technical and organisational measures to ensure data security and protection against accidental or unlawful destruction, accidental loss, alteration, unauthorised disclosure, or access.</p> <p>A comprehensive overview of the technical and organisational measures taken by EGI Foundation can be found at EGI Document 3737: EGI Foundation Technical and Organisational Measures (TOM)</p>
Data Protection Code of Conduct	<p>EGI Foundation is conforming to GEANT Code of Conduct and project members' personal data will be processed in accordance with the Code of Conduct for Service Providers and the EGI-doc-2732-v3: Policy on the Processing of Personal Data.</p>
	<p>This policy is based on AARC Policy development kit (licenced under CC BY-NC-SA 4.0)</p>

Table 3: EGI Privacy Policy for the EOSC Beyond project.